

Adaptation of Improved Hot Pepper (*Capsicum annum* L.) Varieties at Humbo and Bombe Districts of Wolaita Zone, Southern Ethiopia

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Abstract

The trial was conducted in 2019/2020 at Humbo and Bombe districts of Wolaita zone in Southern Ethiopia. The purpose of this study was to test the adaptability and evaluate the yield potential of four improved Hot pepper varieties by comparing with local cultivar. It was laid in Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications and data on plant height (cm), number of branches per plant, number of pods per plant, single pod length (cm), pod weight per plant (gm), marketable yield per hectare (t), unmarketable yield per hectare (t) and total green pod yield per hectare (t) were recorded accordingly. The performance of varieties had showed significant difference among each other. The statistical analysis revealed that total green pod yield per hectare of varieties varied from 4.94t to 8.52 t respectively. An improved varieties Melka Shote (8.52t) and Mareko Fana(8.11t) at Humbo and Mareko Fana (7.74t) and Melka Awaze (6.6t) at Bombe were showed good performance with green pod yield. Although, local cultivar was showed good performance by plant height, number of branches and pod length but it was poor for basic parameters especially marketable and total green pod yield per hectare. In general, Melka Shote, Mareko Fana and Melka Awaze were well adapted and had showed out smarted result in the Humbo and Bombe districts of Wolaita zone for almost all the traits. Therefore, they would be recommended for tested sites and similar agro ecologies.

Keywords: *Adaptation, Hot Pepper, improved varieties, green pod.*

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Introduction

Hot pepper (*Capsicum annum*) originated in the new world tropics and subtropics (Mexico, Central America and Andes of South America) over 2000 years ago (Rodriguez *et al.*, 2008). Even though the exact time of introduction is not certainly known, it has been cultivated in Ethiopia for long period of time. It is grown extensively under various environmental and climatic conditions. It requires a hot and dry climate free of frost and suitable agro ecological areas. Suitable altitude ranges for optimum production is between 1000 and 1800 meters above sea level (MOA, 2016).

Pepper is a very important crop for spice extraction since it has a lot of Oleoresin for dying of food items and Ethiopia is among few developing countries that have been producing paprika and *capsicum* oleoresins for export market (MoARD, 2007). It has been generates cash for smallholder farmers in developing countries such as Ethiopia, Nigeria, and Ghana (Lin *et al.*, 2013. According to the EEPA (2003), pepper generated an income of 122.80 million Birr for farmers in 2000/01 in the major pepper producing regions in the country (Amhara, Southern Nations and Nationality People's Regional State (SNNPR) and Oromia. Currently, it is produced in many parts of the country because, for most Ethiopians food is tasteless without hot pepper. The fine powdered pungent product is an indispensable flavoring and coloring ingredient in the common traditional sauce "Wot", whereas the green pod is consumed as a

vegetable with other food items. The average daily consumption of hot pepper by Ethiopian adult is estimated 15gram, which is higher than tomatoes and most other vegetables MARC (2004).

In 2018 the total cultivated area under pepper in Ethiopia was 8001 hectare with a production quantity of 48890 ton, which indicates, productivity of the crop in Ethiopia is 6.11 t ha⁻¹ (FAOSTAT, 2018), whereas improved varieties released by the national research institutes have given 1.8-2.5 t ha⁻¹ dried pepper and 15 - 20 t ha⁻¹ green pepper at research stations (Gebremeskel et al., 2015; Simon and Tesfaye, 2014).

Despite of its importance, productivity for green and dry pod has stayed low compared to the yield potential of the crop. The major reasons associated with yield reduction are low yield potential of landraces, shortage of improved varieties, poor cultural practices, infestation of disease and pests, and poor post-harvest handling. To alleviate these problems, agricultural research institutions in the country have released improved varieties, like; Melka Shote, Melka Zala, Mareko Fana, Melka Awaze, Oda Dera etc. (MOA, 2016). Although, these varieties were not tested for adaptability potential ant not under production in the Humbo and Bombe districts. The local cultivars under production in these areas were very poor in yield potential. To overcome stated problems and catch up small holder farmers with new technologies, the **study** was carried out with an objective of testing adaptability of improved hot pepper varieties to select and recommend well performed and high yielder varieties for tested and similar agro ecological districts.

Materials and Methods

Description of Study Areas

The study was conducted in 2019/2020 cropping season at Humbo and Bombe districts. Humbo is located 327 km south of the Addis Abeba and 15 km from south of Wolaita Sodo town following the tarmac road that passes through the town to Arbaminch. The study site is geographically located at 6°44'N latitude, 37°48'E longitude and an altitude of 1611meteres above sea level. According to the long-term (1995 – 2017) record of meteorological data, the mean annual rainfall in the area is 1001 mm whereas maximum temperature varies 23.1^oc to 29.81^oC while the minimum temperature from 14^oC to 15.3^oC, with the average value of 20.55^oC. Bombe is one of the twelfth Woreda in the Wolaita Zone and its elevation ranging from1375m to 2277m above sea level. The study site is located at 7°08'15.1"N latitude and 37° 34'54.1"E longitudes with an altitude of 1518 meters above sea level.

Treatments and Statistical Design

The experiment was consisted of four improved hot pepper varieties (Melka Shote, Melka Zala, Mareko Fana, and Melka Awaze) those obtained from Melkasa Agricultural Research Center and one local cultivar, directly from farmers' field. It was laid on Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. Each variety was grown with in a plot size of 7.68m² represented by four rows with 3.2m length. Eight seedlings those ready on raised bade (2mx1m adjacent plots thoroughly prepared, 5cm raised from the surface) for transplanting were hand planted 40cm apart on rows spaced with 60cm. The net plot area used for data recording was 2.88m². Inorganic fertilizers; the blended fertilizer(NPS) was applied at a rate of 200 kg per hectare bases at transplanting while urea was applied at the rate of 100 kg per hectare bases in two splits, the first half at transplanting and the remainder half at hundred percent establishment. Field management practices such as weeding and cultivation were performed uniformly during the growing seasons.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data on plant height (cm) and number of branches per plant were collected at first harvest. Height was measured from surface of soil up to the tip of the main branch. Number primary branches were counted on the basis of main branch, secondary on the basis of primary and tertiary on the bases of secondary

from five representative plants of each plot. A total of four consecutive harvests were made at a week interval. Yield related data, like; number of pods per plant, pod length (cm) and green pod yield per plant (gm) were collected from randomly selected plants. Yield of marketable, unmarketable (mature green pods with visible damages, cracks, blemishes and discoloration due to biotic and abiotic stresses) and total green pods yield per plot (kg) were recorded from net plot area. Total yield (the sum of marketable and unmarketable yield) in plot wise in kilograms was converted into yield ha⁻¹ in tones, like:

$$\text{Yield ha}^{-1} \text{ (t)} = \frac{\text{Yield per plot (kg)} \times 10,000 \text{m}^2}{\text{Net plot area (m}^2\text{)} \times 1000 \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{t}}\right)} \quad (1)$$

Note: 1 ton is equal to 1,000 kilograms. Finally the statistical analysis was performed by using SAS version 9.0 computers statistical software package and mean separation test was done using List Significant Difference (LSD) at 5% probability level.

Results and Discussion

Humbo District

Performance of varieties was significantly different ($P < 0.05$) for all parameters except plant height (Table 1). Statistical analysis revealed that, the highest green pod and marketable yield were obtained from variety Melka Shote (8.52t and 8.28t) followed by Mareko Fana (8.11t and 7.93t) while the lowest yield was from local cultivar (4.94t and 3.96t). Green pod yield from variety Melka Awaze and Melka Zala were statistically non-significant (7.15 and 7.33 tons respectively). In agreement to present study, Dessie and Brihanu(2017) findings of study on growth and yielding potential of hot pepper varieties under rain-fed production at Woreta, was statistically non-significant even if, numerically the highest yield was recorded for Melka Awaze. The local cultivar was the superior with primary, secondary and tertiary branch number among all others whereas, statically non-significant differences were observed between improved varieties for these traits but numerically varied. A highly significant difference was observed among varieties in terms of their green pod number. The highest pod number was recorded from variety Melka Shote (46.66) followed by Melka Awase (31.33) and local cultivar (29.66), while the least pod number for Melka Zala (16.33). The longest pod (26.33cm) was recorded for Melka Zala. The highest single pod weight (175.86gm) was recorded for Mareko Fana whereas the least (3.96t) for local cultivar.

Table 1. Mean Values of Green Pod Yield and Yield Related Traits at Humbo District

No	Cultivars	NoPBr	NoSBr	NoTBr	PH (cm)	NoPP ⁻¹	PL (cm)	WtPP (gm)	MrkYh a ⁻¹ (t)	UnmrkYha ⁻¹ (t)	TGPY ha ⁻¹ (t)
1	Local	9.66	10.66	8.33	54.0	24.66	19.86	78.97	3.96	0.98	4.94
2	Melka Awaze	4.66	7.33	9.33	50.0	31.33	19.03	130.93	6.08	0.39	6.48
3	Melka Shote	5.0	7.0	9.0	45.4	46.66	25.90	163.0	8.28	0.24	8.52
4	Melka Zala	4.66	6.0	6.33	47.93	1633	26.33	133.43	6.05	0.16	6.22
5	Mareko Fana	4.66	6.0	7.66	46.13	25.0	22.40	175.96	7.93	0.18	8.11
	LSD(0.05)	1.417	2.394	0.972	13.189	4.203	6.738	22.676	1.441	0.09	1.479
	CV (%)	13.12	17.18	6.34	14.38	7.49	15.76	8.82	11.84	12.3	11.46

Note: No=number, t=tone, cm=centimeter, gm=gram, NoPBr=number of primary branches, NoSBr=number of secondary branches, NoTBr=number of tertiary branches, PH=plant height, NoPP⁻¹=number of pod/plant, PL=pod length, WtPP⁻¹=weight of pods/plant, MrkYha⁻¹=marketable yield/hectare, UnmrkYha⁻¹=unmarketable yield/hectare and TGPYha⁻¹=total green pod yield/hectare.

Bombe District

The result in Bombe district revealed that performance of improved varieties was significantly different for all most all traits like; weight of single pod, pod length, number of pods per plant, marketable and total green pod yield (Table 2). Statistically, they were non-significantly affected for number of primary, secondary, and tertiary branches, plant height and unmarketable yield. The highest green pod and marketable yield was recorded for Mareko Fana (7.76t and 7.60t) which followed by Melka Awaze (6.60t and 6.42t). The local cultivar was showed superiority by number of branches and unmarketable yield, but the lowest by basic parameters (green pod and marketable yield) for selection (Table 2).

Table 2. Mean Values of Green Pod Yield and Yield Related Traits at Bombe District

No	Cultivars	NoPBr	NoSBr	NoTBr	PH (cm)	NoPP ⁻¹	PL (cm)	WtPP (gm)	MrkYh a ⁻¹ (t)	Unmrk Y ha ⁻¹ (t)	TGPY ha ⁻¹ (t)
1	Local	5.0	6.0	9.66	50.46	17.66	19.86	20.73	4.86	0.23	5.09
2	Melka Awaze	3.33	4.0	8.0	65.26	19.66	24.23	24.23	6.42	0.17	6.60
3	Melka Shote	4.33	5.33	7.33	46.26	15.33	18.56	18.56	5.78	0.13	5.92
4	Melka Zala	3.33	4.66	7.0	58.20	17.13	21.75	21.75	5.90	0.16	6.06
5	Mareko Fana	3.0	4.66	8.66	52.66	17.0	20.75	20.75	5.60	0.15	7.76
	LSD(0.05)	1.458	1.165	2.782	10.937	1.851	3.464	2.758	1.559	0.052	1.549
	CV (%)	20.38	12.55	18.16	10.54	5.66	8.74	6.90	13.54	15.98	13.08

Conclusion and Recommendation

The outcome of study indicated the presence of significant difference among hot pepper varieties for almost all parameters. Although, the yield of varieties were not meet the national average yield potential of the crop, this may be due to occasion of low environmental potential for crop production, invisible factors at the tested sites and potential of the varieties to adapt the tested environments. Melka Shote and Mareko Fana at the Humbo district whereas, Mareko Fana and Melka Awaze at Bombe district were showed the best performance with marketable yield and total green pod yield. Even though, local cultivar was superior with branch number and plant height, it was very poor for yield and basic yield related components. Therefore, varieties Melka Shote and Mareko Fana would be recommended for Humbo district and Mareko Fana and Melka Awaze for Bombe and similar agro ecologies.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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